

Title: Human-centric emotion recognition in VR for Humanities research

Abstract:

In the rapidly evolving landscape of AI research, particularly within the realm of emotion recognition in immersive environments within challenging domains, such as social sciences and humanities research, the emergence of datasets like VREED has opened new avenues for exploration. VREED was recently published to accommodate research on emotion recognition, encompassing behavioral (eye tracking) and physiological signals, including electrocardiograms (ECG) and Galvanic Skin Responses (GSR), alongside self-reported responses from participants immersed in 360-Virtual Environments.

Although accurate classification models can be achieved with this dataset, it is limited in sample size for the application of contemporary machine learning algorithms, such as Deep Neural Networks (DNN).

This work introduces a new approach to address the inherent challenge of limited sample size when applying state-of-the-art machine learning techniques, such as DNN, to datasets like VREED. The proposed variation of the MixUp data augmentation method not only enhances dataset diversity but also fortifies the robustness of the models, providing a solution to the common issue of overfitting. The designed DNN architecture is meticulously crafted to capture intricate patterns in behavioral (eye tracking) and physiological signals (ECG and GSR) within VR environments. The findings of this work reveal substantial performance improvements compared to the baseline classifiers presented in the original VREED study, contributing significantly to the advancement of emotion recognition methodologies in VR settings relating to social sciences and humanities research.

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